

The Extent Which Information Technology Contributes to the Quality of Hotel Service

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Abstract

The quality of hotel services has great importance in contemporary business and hotels, because of the changes that the world has witnessed and the increase in competition between organizations to provide high-quality services. Improving the quality of services is a very important issue as a result of the pressures that most companies face due to the increase in competitors, customer complaints, or the desire to increase sales. In this context, the purpose of the study tended towards analyzing the reality of the use of information technology in improving the level of hotel services by addressing the concept and quality of hotel service and the extent to which the study sample uses these applications from the point of view of the customers of the searched hotels. In addition to clarifying the dimensions of the quality of hotel services to match specifications needed for those services, a structure has been designed according to previous research methodology, assuming there is a correlation affected by the information technology dimension with the quality of hotel services. The researchers found that the interest in the elements and types of quality did not reach the required level, which led to achieving the dimensions of quality. The current study also found that the majority of hotels have a website that is used to obtain information about competing hotels and customers in order to provide better services and thus achieve a competitive advantage. The hotel management's reliance on bilateral contacts and providing feedback, which is, answering customers' inquiries and giving them the information they need in order to obtain high-quality hotel services.

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1. Introduction

Due to the technological progress that the world is witnessing, especially in the field of business organizations, it has cast a shadow over the operations of hotels and technology in its elements (communications, computers, the Internet) has affected the quality of hotel services and how they are provided to customers, and therefore these hotels must keep pace with this progress and development in the field of technology. This current study sought to clarify the role of information technology on the quality of providing hotel services. It is known that business is now affected by information and competition has become between organizations who own the information and use modern technological means to obtain it. Hotels also practice many businesses to serve customers, as this requires work. A measure of balance between customer satisfaction and service quality in order to achieve the best service that results in the maximum possible attraction to customers, in addition to achieving economic returns that cover the costs of that service with motivational profits for workers and thus the development of service activities. Quality in this activity is a goal that efficient departments aspire to. The strategy that is related to the core hotel operations, and most researchers in strategic studies have promised it an entry point to achieve a Competitive Advantage and expansion in the hotel service market. In this context, researchers' efforts reinforced this trend and emphasized the importance of penetrating the competitive situation through quality of service.

1.1 Hotel Service Concept

The American Marketing Association (AMA) has focused on defining services as intangible products that are exchanged directly from producer to customer and their ownership is not transferred or stored, and they disappear quickly, and services are difficult to define or know because they appear at the same time that they were purchased and consumed, and consist of intangible elements often. It involves customer participation in a specific way, is not transferable, and has no specific character (Bannet 1988, 184). Services are intangible products that mainly aim to satisfy the needs and desires of the customer and achieve benefits for him (Al Mosaed, 2005: 35). The service was also defined as any act or performance that a party can provide to another party and it is basically intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything, and its provision is not linked to a physical product (Kotler, 2000: 428) (Kotler and Keller, 2006, 402). One of the important definitions of hotel service is that it is a group of actions that the systems offer to customers in order to satisfy their needs and desires by providing all the required facilities and then ensuring complete comfort for them (Al-Adwan, 1996: 9). Hotel services also represent a group of activities or businesses offered for sale that the hotel organization provides to its customers, and its aim is to satisfy their needs and desires in order to achieve the goals of the hotel organization of profitability, growth, survival and continuity (Taklan, 2001, 40). As well as the definition provided by (Christopher & Malcolm, 1995: 282) and indicated that the hotel service is a group of activities and processes provided by the hotel that achieve the state of satisfaction and acceptance of the guests in return for a certain amount of money without being associated with any error.

1.2 Hotel Service Marketing Mix

After selecting the customers in the target market, the marketing department in the organization is required to meet the needs and desires of customers in this market, which requires taking decisions that will reach the market through an integrated marketing program that includes a set of elements called the marketing mix. The hotel marketing mix is "a set of tools or marketing elements that can be controlled, and as shown in Table (2), as the

hotel organization works to mix some with others to achieve the desired response in the target hotel market.” (Kotler and Armstrong, 2001: 67) (ali et.al,2020)>

1-Product:

The term product refers to what organizations offer to their current and potential customers in terms of goods, services, or ideas. And the successful marketer must realize the services that are most appropriate for its customers, in terms of their quality and level, and it is not possible for him to do this except by carrying out many marketing functions (Al-Muhtadi, 2003, 38-39), foremost of which is marketing research, developing current products, and studying a cycle The life of the products (Damour, 2005 - 163 164).

2- Distribution:

The essence of the distribution process means how the services reach the prospective customer in the appropriate place or time and how to ensure their awareness and ensure the exchange process on the part of the consumer or industrial buyer, and the location of service providers and how to reach them is an important factor in marketing services.

3- price

It is the process of matching the benefits obtained by the buyer or the consumer with the values that he can pay, and it is a complex process linked to multiple economic and behavioral considerations. Just as a customer buys our products with his money, we also as marketers buy the customer's money with our products .. The price mix is determined based on a study of all factors that confirm costs. Demand and supply, consumer ability to pay, competitors' pricing policies, government legislation and laws, and other elements of the marketing mix.

4- Promotion

Promotion includes communication operations aimed at influencing the target customer in order to win over his buying behavior. The promotion is carried out in many and many ways, the most prominent of which are: advertising, advertising, commercial, personal selling, and means of promoting sales.

5- People

The human element appeared in the original list that Borden described in the traditional marketing mix model under the personal selling item, but the following should be taken into consideration:

A- Individuals who play an important role in operations and production in service institutions (air conditioning in the restaurant, for example) own a part of the security of the service itself, but also contribute to the production of the service just like sales representatives. The distinctive feature of service organizations is that their productive employees perform or maintain the service in addition to their role in selling the service. The method of service delivery or the method of providing it is crucial to selling the service just as it is the case in the traditional selling activity. (Damour and Samara, 2005, 335).

B. The main role: where the service is actually implemented by the provider, such as a dentist or a university professor.

T - The facilitating role: where the workers here facilitate the exchange process and participate in it, such as hotel receptionists or public relations employees in hospitals.

W - The auxiliary (additional) role: The workers play an important role in helping to find the exchange process, but they are not part of it, such as travel agents, brokers and equipment rental services.

6- Physical environment

There are few services in which the physical environment plays any role in the process of market exchange. The components of the existing physical environment will influence the judgment of customers and users of the concerned service organization. The normal environment consists of elements such as furnishing, colors, interior design, decoration, parking lots, packaging and other goods that It includes the process of providing the service (for example, cars that benefit from car rental shops) and other tangible things.

7 - The process of providing services (processes) process

The behavior of employees in service organizations is an important factor, as well as the processes in how the service is provided and delivered, so the welcome, good reception, and attention of the employees helps to overcome the problem of waiting for service or others, but they do not compensate for these problems. The degree of the mechanism used in providing the service, the degree of freedom given to the employees, the degree of customer participation in the service delivery process. The elements of the marketing mix for services appear in Table (2).

process	Physical environment	people	place	promotion	price	product
Activity flows	facilities	workers	channels	Promotion mix	flexibility	Natural advantage
Lines number	equipment	customers	Showing	Selling persons	Price level	Quality level
Customers involvement	Employees uniform	culture	intermediance	Advertising	Differentiation	accessories
-	Physical evidence	Search for employees	transportation	-	discount	packaging
-	-	-	Storing	-	Condition	insurance
-	-	-	Channel management	-	Premium	Production lines

Source : Zeithmal , V., Binter , M., Service Marketing , Intergrating Customer Focus Across . the Firm , International Edition , Mc Graw -Hill, New York,USA .P25 ,2003.

Dimensions of Hotel Services Quality:

The service generally has dimensions through which it can determine its ability to satisfy the needs, and the researchers mentioned five to ten dimensions, including (Russell, Evans, Slack). However, the researchers agree with the five dimensions of quality that Russell identified in Table (3) because it was characterized Comprehensiveness of most of the dimensions mentioned by others (Russell et al., 2000,300). The quality of hotel service has two basic dimensions, namely Technical Quality and Functional Quality, both of which are important to customers and the beneficiaries of the service, as technical quality refers to the quantitative aspects of the service, that is, aspects that are expressed in quantitative terms, while functional quality refers to the behavior of service providers and their way of dealing. With customers. Service quality is also seen as the outcome of interaction between customers and between elements related to the hotel organization, and within this framework, three criteria for the quality of hotel service have been defined (Al-Alaq and Mahmoud, 2002: 16).

A- Physical Quality, which includes the material aspects of the service, such as building design, equipment, and others.

B- Corporate Quality, the reputation and image of the hotel organization among customers

C_ Interactive Quality, which is derived from the interaction between the working individuals and the hotel organization and its customers.

(3) Russell Table Quality dimensions

Concepts	Dimensions	
Commitment to provide the service at the time the visitor likes	durability	1
Desire to immediately assist the guest and provide him with service	Responsiveness	2
Ability to generate and gain guest trust	trust	3
Politeness, respect and affection for personal contact with the guest	empathy	4
The physical guide to the tourist service	Tangibility	5

Source: Russel , Robert Taylor, 2000 (Operation Management) multimedia version , 3rd ed ., prentice- Hall, p 393

Some authors have identified ten dimensions of hotel service quality (Zeithmal & Binter, 2003: 28-31).

- 1- Tangibility. Physical evidence, devices, equipment, personnel appearance, means of communication, etc. to assess the quality of service.
- 2- Reliability. The ability to provide the service on time and with the required accuracy and the extent of fulfilling the obligations.
- 3- Communication. Listen to customers and keep their news in a language they can understand.
- 4- Responsiveness. The ability to deal effectively with complaints and suggestions, and take initiative in providing the service with a welcome source.
- 5- Understanding Tourism Needs. It indicates the extent of the service provider's ability to identify and understand customers' needs and provide them with special care and attention.
- 6- Access. Ease of communication and accessibility.
- 7- Competence. This criterion indicates the level of merit of service providers in terms of skills and experiences that help them provide the service better.
- 8- Credibility. It indicates the good reputation of the organization and the honesty and sincerity of the service provider in interacting with customers.
- 9- Security. It expresses the degree of safety during the stay at the hotel.
10. Empathy. Personal care for customers, sympathy for their problems and respect for their customs and traditions. That the previous criteria on which to evaluate the quality of hotel service are not necessarily independent of each other, but rather overlap with others, and may be complementary to each other, and are appropriate to evaluate the quality of many services (Steven, 1995) : 160). Table (4) shows the dimensions of quality from the viewpoint of some writers.

2. The concept of information technology

The concepts of information technology (technology) have varied due to the speed of its development on the one hand, the tasks it performs on the other hand, and its entry into the joints of daily life on the third side. Especially in the field of service business organizations such as hotels, as information technology plays a vital and important role in this aspect, as it works to provide and expand the necessary tools and means to facilitate access to and exchange of information and make it accessible to its applicants quickly, accurately and effectively. It has no limits, especially the Internet (Al-Jasem, 2005, 49). (Daft, 2001, 199) asserts in his study that technology refers to "the tools, methods, machines, and methods used in transforming the organization's inputs, including materials, and ideas, into outputs in the form of goods and services." Whereas (Sindi: 2000, 17) defined technology as "the total sum of the knowledge acquired and the experience obtained in the production of goods and services within a specific social and economic scope with the intention of satisfying the needs

of society in terms of goods and services in quantity and quality." As for the encyclopedic dictionary, it defines information technology as (obtaining, processing, storing, and transmitting audio, pictorial, and digital information in a written text, using a combination of microelectronics and computer equipment and telecommunications (Al-Jasem, 2005, 51)). Whereas, UNESCO defines information technology as the fields of scientific, technological, engineering knowledge and management methods used in handling and processing information and its applications. It is related to the interaction of computers and devices with humans and their participation in social and economic matters (Al-Jasem, 2005, 51).

Recently, the term information technology has appeared, to include the current revolution of the current century in the progress of the field of computers and the automation of information systems, which is the information revolution by using modern technological means of communication technology and electronic technology to keep pace with the development of the times, and to meet the human need in a more accurate and flexible manner. And at amazing speed. Information systems perform the same tasks as information technology, but information technology relies mainly on the latest modern technology reached by the human mind that benefits from information systems in all areas of life with tremendous speed, infinite accuracy and flexibility in interaction (Abu Arafa and others, 27, 2006). (Robbins, 1990, 19) has defined it as "the information, equipment and processes required in converting inputs into outputs in various types of organizations, whether industrial or service."

2.2: The importance of information technology

Within this approach, the indicators that highlight the importance of information technology can be summarized as follows (Shore: 1996, 53) (Burhan: 1999, 8):

-Information technology is an effective tool that contributes to reducing the volume of costs allocated to providing production elements (such as raw materials, manpower, and at rates that exceed their previous cost ratios).also Creating new opportunities not witnessed by organizations in introducing new products and services, such as expert systems and decision support systems .and finally Improving customer service by fulfilling their requests by the terminals.

3. Information Technology Objectives

Information technology is a revolution that has spread rapidly in our economy and entered all aspects of organizational life, devoting its basic purposes to achieving full benefit from it in solving all intractable problems, which gives administrative units great effectiveness in improving their ability to perform administrative functions to the fullest, as it is one of the tools of successful modern management (Salmi: 2000, 436).

The main purpose of information technology is to provide the necessary information and organize it to support all programs that work to strengthen the relationships between daily business processes and the planned investments within the appropriate strategies, as information technology has sought to reduce the risks and responsibilities arising from these investments (Al-Araji and Al-Aouneh 2002, 70).

(Hamshari, 2001, 403) defined the objectives behind the use of information technology to achieve the following:

1. Accuracy: It is the ratio of correct information to a set of information produced during a period

Chronological, as accuracy is the most important feature resulting from the use of electronic computers and it compensates for the errors and pitfalls in which the human element falls.

2. Proper timing: in order for information technology to achieve its primary goal of facilitating all daily business processes and providing them when actual need, as it must reach the

beneficiaries as quickly as possible, as the value of information is measured by the degree to which it reaches the beneficiaries in times of urgent need for it to make important decisions. Affects the future functioning of the entire organization.

3. Economy: The basis of the existence of information technology is to provide the appropriate time and accuracy required. However, its real benefit is achieved when the cost of obtaining it is less than its value, as the economics of information is one of the things that must be considered when putting information technology into practice.

4. Comprehensiveness: that is, information technology contains information sufficient to meet the needs of its beneficiaries and support decision-makers to make sound decisions that do not lack full awareness of the topic in all its aspects. However, it must be taken into account that the density of information may sometimes lead to diminishing its importance, and this calls for accompanying The comprehensiveness feature is the feature of brevity thanks to the quick and intensive response to all its users' inquiries.

5. Appropriateness or conformity: The most important goals that information technology aspires to achieve because the degree of suitability of information and its conformity with the needs of its beneficiaries is the most diagnostic factor for the value of the information produced. Here, the role of computers and information technology in this field and of providing them with the necessary information according to their needs.

3.4 Information Technology Components

Researchers have differed opinions as they define the main components of information technology. These discrepancies came as a result of their awareness and awareness of the basic concepts, developments and administrative issues in Information Technology (IT). They are represented by equipment, software, communications, database management and some data processing technology . (O'Brien, 1997, 433) saw that building an information technology infrastructure is the result of strategic plans and creative intellectual design within a basic map that includes the following components:

1. The information base: the formation of a basic base for information technology within the organization requires the provision of all its necessary tools, including hardware, software and modern means of communication that facilitate the work of many organizational units and add to information technology support and attribution for all organizational levels.

2. Sources of information: the establishment of a specialized center affiliated with the organization whose task is to preserve and store information, present it and prepare it when it is actually needed, and provide all the analytical specializations and technical staff.

3. Applications: The most important elements of information technology that enhance the interconnectedness of the processes that take place within the organization and its circles, administrative decision-making, computer cooperation for users, as well as important strategic decisions related to competitive matters and their benefits.

4. Information Technology Management: Information technology planning puts before us important and necessary recommendations for information systems. This requires building an information technology infrastructure and the subsequent re-design to keep pace with any strategy, the organization's philosophy and its own vision.

The following elements of information technology can be mentioned:

a. computer :

Those electronic computers and the physical parts attached to them, which are always in direct contact with the data, update the stored information, process it, and produce the possible results (Al-Taie,

2000, 51). Previously, the task of data processing, storing, retrieving and updating information needed for long periods, relying on traditional (manual) methods that are no longer appropriate and the tremendous increase in the size and quality of data, so that the situation necessitated the necessity of possessing modern information technology means,

foremost of which are electronic computers and microfilm devices. And communication devices.

The statistics have indicated a variation in the quantity and type of computers and physical components available to each country, but this is not a sufficient indicator to measure the extent of the impact of information technology, as the effective use of it and its employees efficiently in the development of administrative work is a measure of the degree of benefit from it (Burhan, 2015, 59).

Machines cannot work alone without the presence of the software, as it is just a deaf machine unable to adopt any benefit or benefit without feeding it and providing it with the programs that will be entered, as the work of the central processing unit for data is based on the set of instructions that it reaches to implement the processing operations through those programs (Al-Tai, 2000, 148). It is a set of orders and instructions directed to computers to process the stored data in a manner that ensures the achievement of the outputs (Brodrick & Bondrean, 1990, 4). These software are also prepared by self-certification or by the beneficiaries or any other external party, and the software needs qualified technical staff. Systems analysis, design and programming. As the software represents the most expensive component compared to the rest of the other parts, and if the costs of these parts decreased, however, the costs of the software preparation and development process continued to rise as it is.

B. The internet

internet: The word internet was derived from the word (interconnection), meaning interconnection, and it has been agreed that the Internet is a very huge network of different networks that are interconnected with each other in various parts of the world. It is not owned by specific individuals, institutions, or governments (Abu Arafa et al., 2006, 141).

3.5 Information technology application requirements

The organizations' adoption of information technology has become a major criterion for their ability to compete in light of the challenges they face and because these technologies have an effective role in obtaining these advantages. 2013,61):

1. The commitment of senior management to adopt these technologies.
2. Creating the necessary infrastructure for the adoption of such technologies.
3. Providing all its technological requirements and its serious participation in running the business.

In the same context, (Musa, 2010, 29) emphasized the following requirements to ensure the success of the application of information technology:

1. Create the necessary theoretical and technical frameworks in terms (quantitative and qualitative) as a tool to provide material and moral incentives for individuals working in information systems, which provides adequate conditions for work and leads to an increase in the sense of satisfaction on the part of workers.
2. Update the required information accurately and clearly to follow all technical developments and continuously to reach a state of innovation and creativity in it.
3. Expanding the use of computers in vital activities, securing all requirements to complete their work, and providing all their needs of backup tools and complementary parts necessary for operation and maintenance to avoid any interruption or delay in the progress of work.
4. Reducing the resistance of human resources due to the changes that occur with the introduction of information technology and the search for methods that reduce their severity and make them support for the application of these technologies.

4. Methodology of the study

1: Research problem

Contemporary hotel establishments face great challenges as a result of developments in their environment, and among the most important of these developments is the continuous

development in the field of hotel services, and the importance of the role that this element can play in the overall dimensions of the administrative process, especially the quality of hotel service. These hotels conduct a continuous review of the modern components they need, as researchers and field studies have confirmed their importance as an important element in improving hotel service quality.

Based on that, the research problem is embodied in the poor perception of hotel establishments in Dohuk governorate of the relationship and the impact of information technology on the quality of the hotel service it provides to customers and the impact that this has on the movement of hotel activity in the governorate of Dohuk.

2- The importance of research:

The importance of research stems from the following:

A- The research deals with the hotel sector in the city of Dohuk, where hotel establishments are of particular importance in the region. And since information technology can play an important role in the quality of the service provided, so informing the stakeholders in this vital sector of the importance of modern technologies contributes to encouraging tourism.

B- Within the limits of the research survey, no researcher has previously dealt with the research variable at the level of hotel establishments in Dohuk governorate, which gains importance in establishing the field side of the research.

3- Research objectives:

A- Study the components of information technology and the extent of their use by hotel establishments, the research sample.

B- A statement of the impact of the information technology components used on the quality of the hotel services provided by the establishments, the research sample.

C- Explain the importance of information technology in developing the quality of hotel services.

4- Research limits:

A- Spatial boundaries: The research included a sample of hotels in Dohuk Governorate.

B- Temporal limits: The temporal limits of the research were represented in the period 1/1/2021 until 6/15/2021.

5- Research hypothesis:

By stating the importance of the research objectives, the hypotheses centered as follows:

A - There is a low level of use of information technology elements in the hotel service provided by hotels.

B - The poor awareness of the hotel administrations operating in the governorate of the importance of information technology and its great role in the quality of hotel services.

5. Analyzing the results and testing hypotheses

A- Information

Table (8) shows that the largest percentage of agreement was on the paragraph related to (b) (The hotel management uses advanced computers to carry out its business and provide good hotel service), reaching (100%) by (29) individuals from the total sample, and this indicates the importance of using The advanced computer and its importance in the hotel business, with an arithmetic mean of (4.69) and a standard deviation of (0.471).

While the factor related to (the use of the computer contributes to the achievement and development of the hotel service provided to customers) ranked second, as the percentage of agreement on this paragraph reached (96.6%) by (29) members of the sample, and this indicates that the computer has great importance in developing the service. Presented to customers, while the percentage of disagreement was (3.4) by (1) member of the sample, and the mean was (4.69) and the standard deviation (0.666)

The factor related to (the current programs used to provide the information that the customer needs) came in third place, with an agreement rate of (86.2%) and by (25) individuals, which is a large percentage, but by comparing it with other factors, this indicates that the provision of information is provided by other means. , And the neutrality rate reached (13.8%) by (4) individuals, while the arithmetic mean was (4.34) and a standard deviation (0.721).

ST. DEVI.	MEAN	strongly disagree 1		disagree 2		Neutral 3		agree 4		Strongly agree 5		VARIBLES
		%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	
1.052	3.97	3.4	1	3.4	1	24.1	7	31	9	37.9	11	X9
0.574	4.52					3.4	1	41.4	12	55.2	16	X10
0.751	4.28					17.2	5	37.9	11	44.8	13	X11
1.017	3.97	3.4	1			31	9	27.6	8	37.9	11	X12

The factor related to (it is possible through computer hardware and software to achieve communication between the hotel management and customers of all kinds (persons, agencies)) came in last place, at a rate of (89.7%) and by 26 members of the sample, and this indicates the great dependence on the computer in achieving operations Communication and access to information and the percentage of neutrality was (10.3%) by 3 members of the sample. The arithmetic mean reached (4.45) and a standard deviation of (0.686).

ST. DEVI.	MEAN	strongly disagree 1		disagree 2		Neutral 3		agree 4		Strongly agree 5		VARIBLES
		%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	
0.471	4.69							31	9	69	20	X1
0.721	4.34					13.8	4	37.9	11	48.3	14	X2
0.686	4.45					10.3	3	34.5	10	55.2	16	X3
0.660	4.69			3.4	1			20.7	6	75.9	22	X4

B: Computer:

We note from Table (9) that the largest percentage of agreement was on the paragraph related to (The hotel’s website on the Internet helps to increase the possibility of managing the hotel and the speed of response to the requests and desires of customers), reaching (96.6%) and by (28) members of the sample, and this indicates To the importance of the hotel’s location for the hotel’s management and for the customers, with a mean of (4.45) and a standard deviation (0.572), while the factor related to came in second place (the hotel has a

website that allows customers to obtain information about the hotel and the type of service provided in it). The percentage of agreement on this paragraph is (93.1%) and by (27) members of the sample, and this indicates the need for the hotel to have a website on the Internet so that customers can obtain information about the hotel and the type of service provided in it, while the percentage of disagreement on this worker is one individual Only of the sample individuals reached the mean (4.48) and a standard deviation (0.738).

c: Communications

Table (10) shows that the largest percentage of agreement was on the paragraph related to (the hotel administration has the system for internal communications to receive requests and suggestions from customers and provide them with the required information), reaching (96.6%) by (28) members of the sample, and this indicates that The hotel administration has an internal communication system to receive customers' requests and suggestions and provide them with the required information. The arithmetic mean of this factor is (4.52) and a standard deviation (0.574). Whereas, the factor related to (helps the hotel's current communication system to respond quickly to the variables that may occur in the internal and external environments) came in second place, as the percentage of agreement on this paragraph reached (82.7%) and by (24) members of the sample and this indicates the contribution The communication system of the hotel on the rapid response to the variables that may occur in the internal and external environment and the arithmetic mean of this factor reached (4.28) and a standard deviation (0.751). The factor related to (availability of the hotel management system for external communication network represented in (telephone, telex, fax, and Thuraya) to meet the needs of customers of all kinds came in third place, where the percentage of agreement reached (68.9%) and by (20) members of the sample and in the middle My account is (3.97) and with a standard deviation (1.052). This indicates the existence of the hotel management system of the external communication network represented in (telephone, fax, telex, etc.) to meet the needs of customers of all kinds.

ST. DEVI.	MEAN	strongly disagree 1		disagree 2		Neutral 3		4 agree		Strongly agree 5		VARIABLES
		%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	
0.738	4.48			3.4	1	3.4	1	34.5	10	58.6	17	X5
0.978	4.21			6.9	2	17.2	5	24.1	7	51.7	15	X6
0.632	4.55					6.9	2	31	9	62.1	18	X7
0.572	4.45					3.4	1	48.3	14	48.3	14	X8

In the last place, the factor related to (the hotel administration uses e-mail for the purposes of correspondence and receiving information from persons, agencies and tourism companies), where the percentage of agreement on this paragraph reached (65.5%) and by (19) members of the sample, and the mean of the account reached (3.97) and a standard

deviation (1.017), and this indicates the use of the hotel management e-mail for the purposes of correspondence and receiving information from persons, agencies and tourism companies.

This leads to rejecting the research hypotheses through the statistical analysis of the study results.

6. Conclusions

The researchers concluded that the use of traditional methods in the search for hotels has become non-existent, and they have been replaced by modern technology, but the utilization rate when using it did not reach the maximum rate, and the utilization rate of it with all of its components did not reach the required level when compared to developed countries. Also, through the work of the study, the researchers found that the interest in the elements and types of quality did not reach the required level, which led to achieving the dimensions of quality at their required levels. Hotels, to a very large degree, depend on the use of advanced computers in carrying out their business. The majority of hotels have a website that is used to obtain information about competing hotels and customers in order to provide better services and thus achieve a competitive advantage. The hotel management's reliance on bilateral contacts and providing feedback, that is, answering customers' inquiries and giving them the information they need in order to obtain high-quality hotel services. There is a weakness in hotels' 'use of e-mail technology to receive customers' requests, such as reservations, and give them information about the hotel services provided by them. The sites used on the Internet are mostly identification sites and are not practical. That is, transactions are not completed on them. And, based on previous findings, the researchers recommend: Taking into consideration the interest in achieving the dimensions and elements of quality in providing services to customers, and taking into account international standards used in hotels with outstanding performance. Hotels must rely more effectively on the use of computer technologies, the Internet, and effective communications to increase the benefit rate, as it leads to an increase in the quality of hotel service. The necessity of developing websites and using modern languages in designing websites and new technical tools in the world of networks, so that the sites will be more effective. Using digital bank transfers and credit cards in hotel transactions. Increasing reliance on the role of e-mail in the hotel business. Relying on internal and external communication systems and providing the Internet in a good, very fast and well-loaded manner.

References

- Ali, A. M., Doski, S. A., & Mohamamed, D. (2020). Evaluating Hotel Service Quality: an exploratory study in the 4 and 5 star hotels in Erbil and Duhok in Kurdistan -Iraq. *newroz journal* 9(1), 121-133.
- Damour, H. H., Samara, A. H. (2005) *Distribution Channels*, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, University of Jordan, Amman-Jordan.
- Abu-Arafa, A., Muhammad, A., & Amer, I. (2006). *Information Technology*, 1st Edition, Harir House for Publishing and Distribution, Amman-Jordan.
- Al-Alaq, B. A. M., Ahmad, M., (2002), the use of the gaps model to explain the relationship between perceived quality of service and beneficiary satisfaction, *Al-Adari journal*.
- Al-Araji, A. M. H. and Alawneh, A. A. M. (2002), The Reality and Effects of Using Computerized Information Technology: A Field Study at the Center of the Jordanian Ministry of Education, *The Arab Journal of Management*, 22 (1).
- Al-Jasem, J. (2005). *Information Technology*, Osama House for Publishing and Distribution, Amman – Jordan.
- Al-Muhtadi, M., and Khader Y. (2003). The Role of Tourism Services Marketing Information System in Enhancing Customer Satisfaction: A Case Study in the Jaan Hotel in Dohuk Governorate, University of Mosul.

- Al-Salmi, A. A. (2000). *Information Technology*, House of Approaches for Distribution and Publishing.
- Al-Taie, H. A. A. (2005). *Hospitality Management*, "A Professional Introduction" Al-Warraaq Foundation for Publishing and Distribution
- Al-Taie, M. A. H. (2000). *Administrative Information Systems*, Dar Al-Kutub for Printing, University of Mosul, Iraq.
- Bannet , P. (1988) , *Dictionary of marketing Terms* , Chicago, American marketing association.
- Burhan, M. N. (2015). Information Technology and Challenges of Arab Public Administration in the Nineties, *The Arab Journal of Administration*, Volume (19), Number (56).
- Christopher , M. & mc Donald , M. (1995). *marketing An introduction* , 1sd Ed , macillan press , Ltd , 1995 .
- Daft, R. L. (2001). *Organization Theory and Design*, South-Western College Publishing, Ohio.
- Hamshari, O. A. (2001), *Modern Management Information Centers for Libraries*, Modern Visions Foundation, Safa Publishing House, Amman, Jordan.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2006). *Marketing management, 12ed* , prentice – hall , new jersey.USA.
- Kotler, P. (2000), *Marketing Management*, Millennium Ed, Hall-International, Inc., U.S.A. Philip Kotler, Armstrong, Gary,(2001), *Marketing An Introduction*, 6thEd, New Jersey.
- Musa, G. F, (2010),. *Modern Trends in Human Resources Management*, Dar Al-Ruaa Al-Asriyya, Amman, 1st Edition.
- O'Brien, J. A. (1997), *Introduction to Information Systems*, 8th ed., Irwin/McGraw-Hill, U.S.A.
- Payne, A. (1996). *The Essence of Service Marketin* ,Prentice .Hall, New York.
- Robbins, S. P. (1990), *Organization Theory Structure Design and Applications*, 3rd ed., Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Russell , R. & taylor , B., (2000), *Operation Management* ,multimedia, 3rd ed. Prentice_hall,.
- Shore B., (1996), Using information technology to achieve a competitive advantage: a study of current and future end, *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, summer.
- Steven, B. & Kins H. (2005). *Service Marketing* Macmillam Business, London.
- Taklan, I. K. (2001), *The Effect of Marketing Information System on the Development of Hotel Services*, An Applied Study at Al Rasheed Hotel, Unpublished Master Thesis, College of Business and Economics, Al-Mustansiriya University, Baghdad.
- Zeithmal , V., binter , M. (2003), *service Marketing , Intergrating customer focus across . The Firm* , International Edition , Mc Graw –Hill, New York .p25.

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